

Citizen Science Hubs

institutional capacity building: science & society

Call for proposals

2024

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SCIENCE
NL

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1 Introduction

In this Call for proposals information is provided about the application procedure for the Citizen Science Hubs funding round. This Call for proposals falls under the responsibility of Open Science NL, part of the Dutch Research Council (NWO).

In this Call for proposals you will find information about the aim of this programme (Chapter 2), the conditions for the grant application (Chapter 3) and how your proposal will be assessed (Chapter 4). This is the information you need to submit a grant application. Chapter 5 states the obligations for grant recipients in the event you are awarded funding. Chapter 6 contains the contact details and Chapter 7 the annexes.

1.1 Background

The Dutch government has made available substantial funding to support the transition to open science in the Netherlands. The aim of the investment is to make open science the norm.

This Call for proposals is part of Open Science NL's first work programme, covering the years 2024-2025. This work programme addresses a comprehensive set of needs of the field related to open science, and provides a strong basis for the implementation of open science in the Netherlands to grow and flourish. The instruments within this work programme address the following priorities:

1. Capacity building,
2. Infrastructure for Open Science,
3. Robust research processes,
4. Evidence base for Open Science,
5. Empowering communities.

The Call for proposals "Citizen Science Hubs" falls under the priority area "Capacity building". This instrument is intended to strengthen and bundle expertise in Citizen Science and Societal Engagement within Dutch research organisations.

1.2 Available budget

The available budget for this Call for proposals is €2,000,000.

1.3 Submission deadline

When you submit your application in ISAAC, you will also need to enter some details online. Therefore, please start submitting your application at least one day before the deadline of this Call for proposals. Applications that are submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration.

The deadline for submitting full proposals is **14th of March 2025**, before 14:00:00 CET.

2 Aim

This chapter describes the aim of the programme and the societal impact.

2.1 Aim of the programme

Open science stands for an open, diverse and inclusive science that also conducts research with and for society. Citizen Science plays an important role in this, as it has the potential to open up the process of doing research for society.

By Citizen Science, we mean in this programme: scientific research that actively involves people from outside academia, i.e. citizens. This can be in partnership or in collaboration with scientists or professionals, and within different stages of research. The intention of Citizen Science is to gain new (scientific) knowledge and insights, and to improve the dialogue between science, society (and policy) (see definition Citizen Science in Open Science NL's programmes [1]).

The aim of this programme is to strengthen the knowledge, expertise, and support for Citizen Science (including science communication) within Dutch research organisations by establishing Citizen Science Hubs. Citizen Science Hubs act as central points of contact where expertise, resources and infrastructure are centralised to effectively support and coordinate Citizen Science. The expertise required within Citizen Science Hubs include, for example, data (management), scientific research (methodologies), dialogue techniques and science communication, design methods, knowledge integration, ethical and legal knowledge, and hands-on experience around participation (experimental expertise) etc. Thus, hubs ensure the embedding of Citizen Science within research organisations.

Aim of Citizen Science Hubs

Examples of activities in which Citizen Science Hubs are expected to engage in are:

- Developing, guiding, monitoring and evaluating Citizen Science projects.
- Developing and offering training and train-the-trainer courses.
- Providing advice on research methods, data collection and management, ethics and quality assurance.
- Establishing, broadening and deepening networks around thematic or regional issues with partners inside and outside of research organisations.
- Developing and/or offering (digital) tools to support Citizen Science projects.
- Making Citizen Science practices and methods visible within research organisations, which could improve the recognition and rewarding of Citizen Science within those research organisations.

Collaboration

Citizen Science focuses pre-eminently on social issues. For optimal societal impact, collaboration between the entire knowledge chain and societal stakeholders is crucial. Therefore, this programme exclusively funds Citizen Science Hubs that are collaborative efforts between multiple (at least two) research organisations. Through this collaboration, organisations can combine their own unique strengths, open up their own networks with partners from outside of research organisations, and thereby provide richer and more diverse support for a wider audience.

Own contribution

Setting up and sustainably embedding a Citizen Science hub also requires effort and expertise from the organisations where the hub will be located. Therefore, in this Call for proposals, a contribution by the research organisation is mandatory. See for more information in section 3.5.

2.2 Societal impact

Citizen Science is both a scientific practice and a form of public participation in the scientific process. Through interaction and collaboration between researchers and people outside of academia, the chance of applying knowledge and of generating societal impact increases. Societal impact means here changes that (partly) result from research-generated knowledge and skills. These changes contribute to the well-being of people, the planet and society now and in future generations.

Within this call, NWO wants to support the capacity for collaboration between science and society through Citizen Science Hubs. This can further increase the societal impact of research. NWO wants to encourage applicants to take a broad view of the potential desired and undesired impact of their project. Therefore, each application must describe the expected impact. The quality of the plan to realise this impact is assessed as part of the assessment criteria (see 4.3).

NWO offers an [e-learning module](#). For more information on NWO's knowledge utilisation policy, see the website: [Knowledge Utilisation | NWO](#).

3 Conditions for applicants

This chapter contains the conditions that are applicable to your grant application. Firstly, it describes who can apply for funding (Section 3.1) and what you can request funding for (Section 3.2). Subsequently, you will find the conditions for preparing and submitting the application (Sections 3.3 and 3.4) and the specific funding conditions (Section 3.5).

3.1 Who can apply

Applicants, provided they hold a master's degree, may apply if they are permanently employed (and therefore have a remunerated employment contract for an indefinite period of time) or have a temporary contract (at least as long as the duration of the project) with one of the research organisations listed below:

- Universities and universities of applied sciences (UAS) as referred to in Article 1.8 paragraph 1 of the Higher Education and Scientific Research Act and universities listed in the [Policy Rules for Universities](#) located in the Kingdom of the Netherlands;
- university medical centres by which is meant academic hospitals as referred to in Article 1.13 paragraph 1 of the Higher Education and Scientific Research Act;
- institutes affiliated to the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) or NWO;
- Naturalis Biodiversity Center;

Persons with a zero-hour employment agreement may not submit a proposal.

It could be the case that the applicant's tenure track agreement ends before the intended completion date of the project for which funding is applied for, or that before that date, the applicant's tenured contract ends due to the applicant reaching retirement age. In that case, the applicant needs to include a statement from their employer in which the research organisation concerned guarantees that the project and all project members for whom funding has been requested will receive adequate supervision for the full duration of the project.

Applicants with a part-time contract should guarantee adequate supervision of the project and all project members for whom funding is requested.

Additional conditions:

- Each application is submitted by at least two applicants, namely a lead applicant and at least one co-applicant. Lead and co-applicants must be from at least two different research organisations.

Each research organisation may only submit one application. Each organisation can therefore be involved in one hub only. The lead applicant can be from either a University of Applied Sciences or from another research organisation listed above.

3.1.1 Main and co-applicants

The main applicant submits the proposal via the NWO web application ISAAC. During the assessment process, NWO will communicate with the main applicant.

After a proposal has been awarded funding, the main applicant will become the project leader and point of contact for NWO. The research organisation of the main applicant is the main beneficiary and will become the official secretary.

Co-applicants have an active role in realising the project. The (sub)project leaders and beneficiary/beneficiaries are jointly responsible for realising the entire project.

3.2 What can be applied for

Per project, a grant amount of at least €400,000 can be applied for. The maximum duration of the proposed project is 4 years. The applicant and co-applicants can claim costs for personnel and material costs. The available budget modules (including the maximum amounts) are listed below. Apply only for funding that is vital to realise the project. The rates and an explanation of these budget modules are given in annex 7.2.

3.2.1 Personnel

Funding may be requested for salary costs of personnel contributing to the project. The amount depends on the type of appointment and the organisation where the personnel is employed.

3.2.1.1 Personnel at a university in the Kingdom of the Netherlands, umc or a research organisation

For personnel working at a university in the Kingdom of the Netherlands, university medical centre (umc) or KNAW or NWO institute, salary costs can be budgeted for the following positions: professor, university (head) lecturer (universitair (hoofd)docent), hub coordinator, community manager, communication manager/advisor, Citizen Science advisor, data manager, and other similar positions.

3.2.1.2 Personnel of universities of applied sciences, and other organisations

It is possible to budget for salary costs of personnel of Universities of Applied Sciences or Naturalis Biodiversity Center for the following functions: lector, (hoofd)docent, hub coordinator, community manager, communication manager/advisor, Citizen Science advisor, data manager, and other similar positions.

3.2.1.3 Students

It is possible to engage students in the project if they are studying at a research organisation as referred to in Section 3.1. You can enter the costs of this as material costs within the project. There is no maximum on the number of students who can participate in the project.

3.2.2 Material costs

Funding may be requested for all project-specific material costs. These costs are subject to a maximum of 20% of the grant amount.

3.3 Preparing an application

The steps involved in writing your application are:

- download the application form from the NWO web application ISAAC or from the NWO web page (on the grant page of the funding instrument concerned);
- complete the application form;
- save the application form in ISAAC as a PDF file and upload it with any compulsory annexes;
- fill in the requested information online in ISAAC.

Annexes:

- budget (mandatory)
- mutual statement of own contribution of at least 1,5 FTE (mandatory)
- statement of adequate project supervision (if applicable, see section 3.1)

The appendix must be drawn up in accordance with the template provided by NWO. Annexes must be uploaded in ISAAC separately from the application. The budget must be submitted in ISAAC as an Excel file. All of the other annexes, except for the budget, must be submitted as PDF files (without encryption). Any annexes other than those stated above are not permitted.

You must write your application in English.

An application can only be submitted via the web application ISAAC. Applications that are not submitted via ISAAC will not be taken into consideration.

As the main applicant, you are required to submit the application via your own personal ISAAC account.

It is important to start with your application in ISAAC on time:

- if you do not yet have an ISAAC account, then you should create this on time to prevent any possible registration problems;
- any new research organisations must also be added to ISAAC by NWO;
- you also need to submit other details online.

Applications submitted after the deadline will not be taken into consideration by NWO.

For technical questions, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk, see contact (Chapter 6).

Does a main and/or co-applicant work at a research organisation that is not included in the ISAAC database? You can report this via relatiebeheer@nwo.nl so that the research organisation can be added. This will take several days. It is therefore important that you report this at least one week before the deadline.

Applicants are expected to have informed the research organisation where they work about submitting the application and that the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this Call for proposals.

3.4 Conditions for submission

3.4.1 Formal conditions for submission

NWO will assess your application against all the conditions set out in this Call for proposals, including the conditions listed below. Your application will only be admitted to the assessment procedure if it meets these conditions. After submitting your application, NWO requests you to be available to implement any possible administrative corrections so that you can (still) meet the conditions for submission.

These conditions are:

- the main applicant and co-applicant(s) meet the conditions stated in Section 3.1;
- the application complies with the DORA guidelines as described in Section 4.1;
- the application is submitted via the main applicant's ISAAC account;
- the application is received before the deadline;
- the application is written in English;
- the application budget is drawn according to the terms of this Call for proposals (using the format made available which includes the most recent rates);
- the proposed project has a duration of maximum 4 years;
- all required annexes, after a possible request for additions or changes, have been completed and submitted completely and according to the instructions and in accordance with the terms of this Call for proposals.

3.5 Conditions on granting

The [NWO Grant Rules](#) are applicable to all applications.

3.5.1 Compliance with the National Knowledge Security Guidelines

World-class science can benefit from international cooperation. The National Knowledge Security Guidelines (hereafter: the Guidelines) helps knowledge institutions to ensure that international cooperation can take place securely. Knowledge security concerns the undesirable transfer of sensitive knowledge and technology that compromises national security; the covert influence of state actors on education and research, which jeopardises academic freedom and social safety; and ethical issues that may arise in cooperation with countries that do not respect fundamental rights.

Applicants are responsible for ensuring that their project complies and will continue to comply with the Guidelines. By submitting an application, the applicant commits to the recommendations stipulated in these Guidelines. In the event of a suspected breach of the Guidelines in an application submitted to NWO for project funding, or in a project funded by NWO, NWO may ask the applicant to provide a risk assessment demonstrating that the recommendations in the Guidelines have been taken into consideration. If the applicant fails to comply with NWO's request, or if the risk assessment is in apparent breach of the Guidelines, this may affect NWO's grant award or decision-making process. NWO may also include further conditions in the award letter if appropriate.

The National Knowledge Security Guidelines can be found on the central government website at: [Home | National Contact Point for Knowledge Security \(loketkennisveiligheid.nl\)](#).

3.5.2 Scientific integrity

In accordance with the NWO Grant Rules, the project that NWO funds must be carried out in accordance with the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2018). By submitting the proposal, the applicant commits to this code. In the case of a (possible) violation of these standards during a project funded by NWO, the applicant should immediately inform NWO of this and should submit all relevant documents to NWO. More information about the code of conduct and the policy regarding research integrity can be found on the website: [Scientific integrity | NWO](#).

3.5.3 Ethical statement or licence

The applicant is responsible for determining whether an ethical statement or licence is needed for the realisation of the proposed project. The applicant should ensure that this is obtained from the relevant institution or ethics committee on time. The absence or presence of an ethical statement or licence at the time of the application process has no effect on the assessment of the application. If the project is awarded funding, then the grant is issued under the condition that the necessary ethical statement or licence is obtained before the latest start date for the project. The project cannot start until NWO has received a copy of the ethical statement or licence.

3.5.4 Nagoya Protocol

The Nagoya Protocol ensures an honest and reasonable distribution of benefits emerging from the use of genetic resources (Access and Benefit Sharing; ABS). Researchers who make use of genetic sources from the Netherlands or abroad for their research should familiarise themselves with the Nagoya Protocol ([Home - ABS Focal Point](#)). NWO assumes that researchers will take all necessary actions with respect to the Nagoya Protocol.

3.5.5 Openness of the assessment procedure

Transparency is central to open science. For this Call for proposals, Open Science NL will publish both the awarded and rejected full applications and the motivation of the evaluation committee via the website, if the applicants agree to this. Willingness to share this data or not will not be considered in the decision to grant or reject the proposal. Consent for sharing will be requested from the applicants after the decision for funding has been made.

3.5.6 Sharing results

Open Science NL finds it important that the results of all projects are shared, including projects that do not produce the anticipated results. A public summary of all funded projects will be published online. At the end of each project, Open Science NL will request a short report that will also be published online.

3.5.7 Own contribution from applicant's research organisations

This impulse funding is insufficient on its own for the successful establishment and sustainable embedding of a new Citizen Science Hub. Existing staff and expertise at the research organisations are needed in order to effectively utilise the funding, supervise the newly appointed staff, and start providing the services described in the project plan as soon as possible. Therefore, the applicant's research organisations commit to jointly providing their own contribution of at least 1.5 FTE of existing staff with relevant substantive expertise in the area of the application. These personnel will be relieved from their existing workload for the stated number of FTEs to dedicate their time to concrete tasks identified within the project plan.

The own contribution is confirmed through a joint declaration by the submitting research organisations (see section 3.3). There is no minimum or maximum contribution per organisation. The expertise and appropriateness of the personnel is assessed in the assessment criteria (see section 4.3).

4 Assessment procedure

This chapter first describes the assessment according to the DORA principles (Section 4.1) and the course of the assessment procedure (Section 4.2). Second, it states the criteria that the assessment committee will use to assess your application (Section 4.3).

The NWO Code for Dealing with Personal Interests applies to all persons and NWO employees involved in the assessment and/or decision-making process ([Code for Dealing with Personal Interests | NWO](#)).

NWO strives to achieve an inclusive culture where there is no place for conscious or unconscious barriers due to cultural, ethnic or religious background, gender, sexual orientation, health or age ([Diversity and inclusion | NWO](#)). NWO encourages members of an assessment committee to be actively aware of implicit associations and to try to minimise these. NWO will provide them with information about concrete ways of improving the assessment of an application.

4.1 The San Francisco Declaration (DORA)

NWO is a signatory to the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). DORA is a worldwide initiative that aims to improve the way research and researchers are assessed. DORA contains recommendations for research funders, research organisations, scientific journals and other parties.

DORA aims to reduce the uncritical use of bibliometric indicators and obviate unconscious bias in the assessment of research and researchers. DORA's overarching philosophy is that research should be evaluated on its own merits rather than on the basis of surrogate measures, such as the journal in which the research is published.

When assessing the scientific track record of applicants, NWO makes use of a broad definition of scientific output.

NWO requests committee members not to rely on indicators such as the Journal Impact Factor or the h-index when assessing applications. Applicants are not allowed to mention these in their applications. You are, however, allowed to list other scientific products besides publications, such as datasets, patents, software and code, et cetera.

For more information on how NWO is implementing the principles of DORA, see [DORA | NWO](#).

4.2 Procedure

The application procedure consists of the following steps:

- submission of the proposal;
- admissibility of the proposal;
- Pre-advice assessment committee;
- rebuttal;
- assessment committee meeting;
- decision-making.

An external, independent assessment committee will be assigned for this Call for proposals, consisting of representatives from science and practice with knowledge of the field.

The task of the assessment committee is to assess the applications and the relevant documents that are submitted, in conjunction with each other and with regards to both the respective merits of each application and the assessment criteria outlined in this Call for proposals.

Due to the expertise present in the assessment committee, NWO has decided with regards to the assessment of these applications to exercise the option outlined in Article 2.2.4, paragraph 2, of the NWO Grant Rules, to assess all applications without involving referees.

4.2.1 Submission of a proposal

For the submission of the proposal, a standard form is available on the funding page of this Call for proposals on the NWO website. When you write your proposal, you must adhere to the questions stated on this form and the procedure given in the explanatory notes. You must also adhere to the conditions for the maximum number of words and pages.

Your complete application form must have been received before the deadline via ISAAC (see Section 1.3). After this deadline, you can no longer submit a proposal. After submitting the proposal, the main applicant will receive a confirmation of receipt.

4.2.2 Admissibility of the proposal

As soon as possible after you have submitted your proposal, you will hear from NWO whether or not your proposal will be taken into consideration. NWO will determine this based on several administrative-technical criteria (see the formal conditions for submission, Section 3.4). NWO can only take your proposal into consideration if it meets these conditions.

Please bear in mind that within two weeks after the submission deadline, NWO may approach you with any possible administrative corrections that need to be made so that your proposal can (still) meet the conditions for submission. You will be given one opportunity to make the corrections, and you will be given five working days to do this.

4.2.3 Pre-advice assessment committee

After this, your proposal and your rebuttal will be submitted for comments to several members of the assessment committee (the pre-advisers). The pre-advisers will provide a written substantive and reasoned response to the proposal. They will formulate these comments based on the substantive assessment criteria (see Section 4.3.1) and will give the proposal a numerical score per assessment criterion. For this, the NWO score table will be used (on a scale of 1 to 9, where "1" is excellent and "9" unsatisfactory).

4.2.4 Rebuttal

The main applicant subsequently receives the anonymised pre-advice. You then have the opportunity to formulate a rebuttal. You will be given ten working days to submit your rebuttal via ISAAC. If you decide to withdraw the proposal, then you should do this as quickly as possible by sending an email stating this to the office and withdrawing the proposal in ISAAC. If NWO receives your rebuttal after the deadline, then it will not be included in the rest of the procedure.

4.2.5 Meeting of the assessment committee

The committee will make its own assessment based on the available material. Although the pre-advice will 'guide' the final assessment to a large extent, it will not be blindly accepted without question by the committee. The committee will consider and compare the arguments of the pre-advice (also amongst each other) and examine whether the rebuttal contains a well-formulated response to the critical comments from the pre-advice.

Following the discussion, the committee draws up a written recommendation addressed to the Open Science NL Steering Board about the quality and ranking of the proposals. This recommendation is based on the assessment criteria. The proposal must receive an overall qualification of at least “very good” to be eligible for funding. The proposal must also receive at least the qualification “very good” for each of the individual assessment criteria.

For more information about the qualifications, see [Applying for funding, how does it work? | NWO](#).

If, after the discussion of the full proposals, two or more of the full proposals cannot be distinguished from each other based on their weighted total score, then this will result in an ex aequo situation (see Section 4.2.17).

4.2.6 Ex aequo

NWO understands ex aequo to be a situation in which two or more proposals based on their weighted score cannot be distinguished from each other. An ex aequo situation is relevant with respect to the borders of the available budget or the selection borders. The existence of an ex aequo situation is determined as follows. The starting point in this process is the ranking drawn up by the assessment committee, with the final scores rounded down to two decimal points. The reference score here is the score of the lowest-ranked proposal within the borders of the available budget or the selection borders. All proposals with a score that is within 0.05 or less of the reference score will be considered. In this way, the proposals that are equal within a score of 0.1 will be selected. If an ex aequo situation occurs at the borders of the available budget or the selection borders, then, to help increase the number of women working in the scientific field, the proposal from a female applicant will end as the highest. If the ex aequo situation is not resolved via this procedure, then the proposal with the highest score for the criterion ‘quality of the team’ will be ranked highest. If the proposals subsequently still remain tied, then the assessment committee, with the help of an (anonymous) majority vote, will determine the ranking (in accordance with Article 2.2.6, paragraph 5 of the NWO Grant Rules). If this vote also fails to provide a resolution, or if it is deemed to be undesirable to vote, then the ex aequo situation will be sent onto the decision-making body.

4.2.7 Decision-making

Finally, the Open Science NL Steering Board will assess the procedure followed as well as the advice from the assessment committee. They will subsequently determine the final qualifications and decide over awarding or rejecting the proposals.

4.2.8 Timetable

Below, you will find the timetable for this Call for proposals. During the current procedure, NWO might find it necessary to make further changes to the timetable for this Call for proposals. You will be informed about this in time.

Proposals	
14 th March 2025, 14:00:00 CET	Deadline proposals
April 2025	pre-advice consulted
May 2025	Applicants can submit a rebuttal
June 2025	Assessment committee meeting
September 2025	Decision by the board

4.3 Criteria

4.3.1 Assessment criteria

The applications submitted within this Call for proposals will be substantially assessed based on the following criteria:

Criterion 1: Quality of the team composition (30%).

- Do the applicants have the necessary expertise, experience, and network to build a successful hub? This applies to both Citizen Science and science communication.
- Do the applicants have apparent practical experience guiding Citizen Science projects?
- Do the team members, whose capacity is provided in-kind, have relevant expertise? To what extent does their expertise contribute to achieving the goals?

Criterion 2: Quality of the project plan (40%).

- Are the plans to set up the hub substantiated and realistic?
- Is there a concrete description of the services and tasks the hub will perform and the extent to which it will build on existing offerings (in the short and long term)?
- Is the organisational structure and the embedding in the applicants' research organisations well substantiated?
- Are the plans to embed the hub long-term within the applicant research organisations substantiated?
- Is the proposal's budget appropriate and clearly justified?

Criterion 3: Existing network and network expansion (20%)

- What existing and developing networks will the hub serve, and are these appropriate to the hub's tasks and the services it will offer? Are the societal organisations to be involved (regional and national) relevant and appropriate?
- Is there a clear communication strategy for the hub and for network expansion?
- Do the applicants have a good strategy for the hub for aligning tasks and working methods around local and thematic issues with internal and external partners?

Criterion 4: Impact (10%)

- What is the quality of the plan to realise the expected impact of the hub on science, society, and/or business? How will this impact be monitored and how will the approach be adjusted when necessary?

5 Obligations for grant recipients

This chapter details the various obligations that - in addition to the conditions stated in Section 3.5 - apply after funds have been awarded.

5.1 Additional terms and conditions

5.1.1 Socially responsible licensing

The knowledge that emerges from the project could be suitable for use in society. When agreements about licensing and/or the transfer of research results developed under this Call for proposals are made, due consideration should be given to the ten principles for socially responsible licensing, as stated in the NFU factsheet "[Ten principles for Socially Responsible Licensing | NFU](#)".

5.1.2 Supervision and monitoring committee

After the project has been awarded funding, a committee will be appointed in accordance with Article 3.3.2.a of the NWO Grant Rules to supervise and monitor the project. The committee will follow the execution of the project and advise on its progress. More information about this committee will be provided in the award letter.

The committee will facilitate mutual exchange of insights and experiences within the awarded hubs.

Open Science NL wants to monitor the development together with the awarded hubs and the committee in a way that suits the hubs. After being awarded, together with the hubs and the committee, it will be determined how the hubs can continue to grow and how the committee can monitor this.

The hubs report annually on their progress based on a monitoring framework. The hubs themselves establish a monitoring framework with tailor-made agreements. Based on these self-evaluations, annual progress meetings take place between the (delegates of the) committee and the hubs.

5.1.3 Open Access

NWO is committed to making the results of scientific research funded by NWO freely accessible via the internet (Open Access). NWO thereby fulfils the Dutch government's policy to make all publicly funded research open access. Scientific publications of research funded based on allocations resulting from this Call for Proposals should therefore be available in Open Access according to the Open Access Policy. For a further explanation of NWO's Open Access policy see: [Open Science | NWO](#). Other products resulting from projects funded through this Call for proposals should also be shared as openly as possible under an open licence. Examples include presentations, reports, working papers, posters, etc.. It is advised to share these outputs via a trusted repository, such as registered on [OpenDOAR](#).

6 Contact and other information

6.1 Contact

6.1.1 Specific questions

For specific questions about this Call for proposals, please contact:

Frederike Schmitz

Tel nr: +31 6 51 38 95 75

E-Mail: CSHubs@nwo.nl

6.1.2 Technical questions about the web application ISAAC

For technical questions about the use of ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Please read the manual first before consulting the helpdesk. The ISAAC helpdesk can be contacted from Monday to Friday between 10:00 and 17:00 hours on +31 (0)70 34 40 600. However, you can also submit your question by email to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will then receive an answer within two working days.

6.2 Other information

The whole text of this Call for proposals has been published in both Dutch and English. The Dutch version is deemed authentic. For legal interpretation the text of the Dutch version will be decisive.

NWO processes data from applicants received in the context of this Call in accordance with the NWO Privacy Statement, [Privacy Statement | NWO](#).

NWO might approach applicants for an evaluation of the procedure and/or research programme.

7 Annex(es):

7.1 Budget modules and rates

7.1.1 Staff

Non-scientific personnel

Funding may be requested for non-scientific personnel (NWP) necessary to implement the project. The use of NWP must be described in the application.

The duration of the appointment should not exceed the duration of the NWO-funded project.

Rates will be determined using the *Handleiding Overheidstarieven* [HOT-Manual Dutch Government rates], table 2.2 average total labor costs by salary scale, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excluding VAT' for university of applied sciences and NCB Naturalis and Table 2.1 average direct labor costs, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excluding VAT' for Universities, umcs and KNAW and NWO institutes. The salary scale of the requested position determines the rate from the HOT table.

(Head) teachers, lectors and professors

Funding can be requested for salary costs of (senior) lectors and professors at universities, PCs and universities of applied sciences. The use of (senior) lectors and professors must be described in the application. Supervision for a PhD student or postdoc is not eligible for funding.

The duration of the appointment should not exceed the duration of the NWO-funded project.

Rates will be determined using the *Handleiding Overheidstarieven* [HOT-Manual Dutch Government rates], Table 2.2 average total labor costs by salary scale, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excluding VAT' for university of applied sciences and NCB Naturalis and Table 2.1 average direct labor costs, column 'Hourly rate productive hours, excluding VAT' for Universities, umcs and KNAW and NWO institutes. The salary scale of the requested position determines the rate from the HOT table. For professors, scale 17 applies.

Students

Students may be used for research. If the students contribute as part of their curriculum, the rate according to the usual internship allowance of the university or university of applied science applies.

If students contribute as a secondary job in addition to their studies as student assistants, the rate according to HOT table 2 scale 1 applies.

7.1.2 Material costs

Funding can be requested for all project-specific costs related to, among others, consumables, purchase of services, materials, small instruments, access to (inter)national facilities, software and research equipment that have no economic value after use. Costs for travel and accomodation (national and international) for all people working on the project incl. foreign guest researchers, costs for organising (international) workshops and symposia and costs for data management and publications may also be budgeted under this module.

Travel costs (national and international) will only be reimbursed on the basis of second class/economy class tariffs. For publications, the provisions in section 4.5 Open access apply. Costs for an audit can only be budgeted for institutions that are not subject to the educational audit protocol by the Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, with a maximum of €5,000 per audit.

Costs that are not eligible for funding are:

- organisational infrastructure and overhead, including a fully functioning workplace, housing, office automation, personnel administration, commuting expenses, training, facilities, HR advice and business care, information management and home office allowances.
- use and maintenance of in-house developed scientific infrastructure.
- regular educational activities.

7.2 Indexing

The rate at the time of the decision date applies. NWO will, if necessary, apply a one-off indexation of personnel costs when awarding the grant. The date on which the rates take effect is used for this purpose. If the date of publication of the fees is later than the effective date, the date of publication is used. The tariffs of the Universities of the Netherlands (UNL) usually take effect on 1 July, of the Dutch Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU) on 1 August and of the Government Tariffs Manual (HOT) on 1 January.

The on-off indexation does not affect the grant ceiling and the maximum grant amount to be applied for. The grant ceiling and maximum requestable grant amount remain unchanged during the assessment procedure. If awarded, one-off indexation will be applied to the grant amount.

If co-funding is required or permitted, the one-off indexation does not affect the requirements for own contributions and co-funding, nor the IP rights that may result from the co-funding.

7.3 Definition of Citizen Science in this Call

In Open Science NL programmes, the term Citizen Science is used as an umbrella term for ‘collaborative scientific research done by people from inside and outside academia’. Citizen Science initiatives can vary widely, depending on the research domain, the nature of the tasks, the context, and the role of the participants¹.

Citizen Science participants

People of all ages, genders and cultural or social background can collaborate in Citizen Science initiatives. Participants can contribute to different stages of the scientific process, from setting research agendas to co-analysing data and co-creating and communicating outputs.

Citizen Science increases the chance of societal impact

Data and results from Citizen Science are shared openly, respecting legal and ethical standards. But Citizen Science initiatives not only produce scientific results, but they can also offer participants opportunities for enjoyment, learning, social contact, and policy influence. The inclusive approach can help democratise science, promote public engagement and increase the societal impact of research.

The crucial role of communication

Transparent communication about project goals and about participants' roles and expectations is important for effective Citizen Science initiatives. This also includes continuous feedback, fostering dialogue and interaction with participants. Science communication, as ‘two-way communication between researchers and society’² is therefore also a crucial part of any Citizen Science initiative. In the Netherlands, the English term ‘Public Engagement’ or ‘Societal Engagement’ is often used to emphasise dialogue and exchange. These terms

¹ Haklay, M., Motion, A., Balázs, B., Kieslinger, B., Greshake Tzovaras, B., Nold, C., Dörler, D., Fraisl, D., Riemenschneider, D., Heigl, F., Brounéus, F., Hager, G., Heuer, K., Wagenknecht, K., Vohland, K., Shanley, L., Deveaux, L., Ceccaroni, L., Weißpflug, M., Wehn, U. (2020). ECSA's Characteristics of Citizen Science. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3758668>

² Verkade, A., & Smeets, I. (2023). Nationaal Expertisecentrum Wetenschap & Samenleving – Plan van aanpak. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7763918>

underline the use of interactive, dialogue-oriented, and participatory means, rather than one-way communication in the form of sending information ('dissemination').

Overlap with other terminology

As an umbrella term, Citizen Science also has considerable overlap with transdisciplinary research, community-based participatory research, participatory action research, crowdsourcing, and other terms³. However, these terms will not be used in Open Science NL's programmes.

What is not Citizen Science?

Any research practice that treats participants outside of academia only as research objects (e.g. clinical studies) or only as data sources (e.g. as subjects, survey participants, etc.), without further actively involving these people in the research (process) is considered outside of scope for Citizen Science in this call.

The definition was co-written by Open Science NL's Citizen Science/Societal Engagement advisory panel.

³ For an overview of related terminology see: Wehn U, Ajates R, Mandeville C, Somerwill L, Kragh G, Haklay M. 2024 Opening science to society: how to progress societal engagement into (open) science policies. R. Soc. Open Sci. 11: 231309. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.231309>

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